

A QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS OF RESILIENCE TRAINING'S INFLUENCE ON ARMY NATIONAL GUARDSMEN RESILIENCE AND PERFORMANCE

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Abstract: Soldiers in the Army National Guard experience elevated perceptions of stress when compared to their Active Duty counterparts. This study examined quantitative data regarding perception of resilience, application of resilience, and performance for National Guard soldiers that attended a two-week resilience intervention. This study built upon a framework of resilience theory as viewed through the lens of Adult Learning Theory to introduce resilience skills to National Guard soldiers. The study examined the performance data and self-reported perception and application data of 87 soldiers that attended the fiscal year 2019 Wellness Camp intervention from the research methodology and design lens of a quantitative, quasi-experimental, ex post facto study. This study analyzed pretest and posttest data from perception of resilience, and application of resilience skills (goal setting, emotion control, imagery, and energy activation) to fitness endeavors using a two-way ANOVA. This study's results indicated that a statistically

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significant relationship was found between the intervention, pre-, and post-intervention results: perception of resilience 1.76 (SD=4.95), $F(1,86)=10.99$, $p<0.001$; application of goal setting 0.72 (SD=0.91), $F(1,86)=54.54$, $p<0.001$; application of emotion control 0.28 (SD=0.51), $F(1,86)=27.15$, $p<0.001$; application of imagery 0.65 (SD=0.68), $F(1,86)=80.25$, $p<0.001$; and application of emotion control 0.53 (SD=0.68), $F(1,86)=52.77$, $p<0.001$. The outcomes of this study hold potential in making recommended changes to Army doctrine on resilience training frequency.

Introduction

The modern definition of resilience identified a process of adaptation surrounding one's ability to positively adapt to stress and thrive during times of adversity (Dray et al., 2017; Lines et al., 2019; Luthar et al., 2000; Harms et al., 2013; Reivich et al., 2011; Tusaie & Dyer, 2004; Van Breda, 2018). By defining resilience as a process, researchers have established that resilience is not simply a fixed internal state but rather something that can be learned and adapted. The modern view of resilience argued that anyone can learn and develop improved levels of resilience (Dray et al., 2017; Lines et al., 2019; Van Breda, 2018).

Lower levels of perceived resilience have been suggested to increase perception of stress and have been associated with actions and behaviors that negatively affect health and fitness (Lester et al., 2011b; Nindle et al., 2018). Service members experience elevated perceptions of stress in comparison to populations with similar experiences, such as Department of the Army civilians and military spouses (Thomas et al., 2018).

It has been noted that National Guard soldiers struggle more post-deployment than their Active Duty peers with stress-coping and depression (Arbisi et al., 2012; Kline et al., 2014; Russell et al., 2019). Researchers have suggested

that the increased perception of stress in the National Guard is associated with decreased levels of social support when compared to their Active Duty counterparts (Arbisi et al., 2012; Hofscher et al., 2017; Kline et al., 2014; Morgan et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2018). While psychological stress has been linked to negative physiological changes that affect performance, it has recently been suggested that there are also effects on self-efficacy and motivation (Black et al., 2017; Cacioppo et al., 2015). Cassidy (2015) suggested that self-efficacy as a sub-component to resilience can help to mediate the negative effects associated with limited social support. Examining the issue through the lens of these data, the casual relationship between resilience, stress adaptation, and self-efficacy in service members was exposed.

In response to the increased stressors experienced by soldiers and the noted increase in behavioral health concerns, the United States Army created the Comprehensive Soldier Fitness (CSF) Program to develop a process to give soldiers coping skills well in advance of when they will need them (Casey, 2011; Crabtree-Nelson & DeYoung, 2017; Kent et al., 2015; Reivich et al., 2011; Zamorski et al., 2018). The CSF combined efforts with the University of Pennsylvania's Applied Positive Psychology program to develop the Army's Master Resilience

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Training (MRT) curriculum and certification course for soldiers (Reivich et al., 2011).

Army doctrine had set minimum standards for frequency of MRT training for both the Active Duty and National Guard components of the Army. Headquarters, Department of the Army (HQDA) (2014; 2017a) required soldiers of the Active Duty to receive 12 of the MRT curriculum skills at a rate of one skill a month, and soldiers of the National Guard to receive 12 of the MRT curriculum skills at a rate of one skill every other month. This was interpreted by the author to state that Army Doctrine dictates that National Guard soldiers receive less frequent resilience training than their Active Duty counterparts.

In response to concerns surrounding the notable increase in stressors experienced by this component of the Army, many of the 54 states and territories' National Guard Ready & Resilient (R2) Programs had initiated a two-week Wellness Camp as a resilience-based intervention. This initiative was designed to address resilience and self-efficacy through adaptations in stressor coping, enhance perception of resilience, and to modify behavior to support enhanced training and performance by empowering soldiers to make healthy decisions.

Statement of the Problem

This study addressed the effectiveness of a resilience-based resolution. There are resilience enhancing outcome benefits of motivation and initiating behavior associated with self-efficacy (Burger & Samuel, 2017; Lane et al., 2004; Schwarzer & Warner, 2013; Williams, 2010). This study examined a population of soldiers that had attended a Wellness Camp resilience-based intervention for

the effects of self-efficacy, resilience, and behavior change.

Soldier perception of resilience has been shown to be related to previous positive or negative performances (Lester et al., 2011a; Lester et al., 2011b). While increases in soldier perception of resilience have been associated with improvements in mental & cognitive stress adaptation, a soldier's resiliency can also be affected by their physical activity demands and social support structure (Arbisi et al., 2012; Hofscher et al., 2017; Kline et al., 2014; Morgan et al., 2018; Seyed Hojjat et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2018).

The Army's MRT program has been shown to be effective in increasing resilience and psychological health through self-efficacy in the Active Duty Army (Harms et al., 2013; Lester et al., 2011c). It was the intent of this study to correlate the effects of resilience training on self-efficacy, through perception of resilience and application of performance enhancement resilient strategies in the National Guard population. National Guard soldiers have demonstrated a decrease in ability to return to mental and physical peak performance after exposure to stressors in garrison, civilian life, and combat zones (Arbisi et al., 2012; Hofscher et al., 2017; Kline et al., 2014; Morgan et al., 2018; Seyed Hojjat et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2018). This study addressed this concern by increasing the frequency of resilience training in this study population.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this quantitative, quasi-experimental, ex post facto, survey-based study was to examine the effectiveness of a modified method and frequency for administration of the MRT curriculum for Army National Guard

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soldiers. This study sought to establish the statistical significance surrounding effectiveness of the curriculum administration plan in affecting soldiers' perception of resilience and the application of performance enhancement resilience skills such as: goal setting, emotional control, imagery, and energy activation to support successful performance in fitness testing.

Significance of Study

This study provided positive outcomes in multiple areas of resilience, self-efficacy, and operational readiness. This study addressed a concern surrounding the resilience training frequency of the National Guard when comparing the doctrinal differences in required resilience training between Active Duty and the National Guard, and the link between resilience and self-efficacy (Russell et al., 2019). This study held the potential to identify a more beneficial resilience training frequency for the National Guard that could be considered for doctrinal adaptation.

Literature Review

Contemporary literature supported the use of resilience training as an intervention to increase self-efficacy in both the mental and physical domains (Black et al., 2017; Cacioppo et al., 2015; Cassidy, 2015; Lester et al., 2011c; Nindle et al., 2018; Nindle et al., 2013). Resilience training has been associated with positive adaptation to stressors resulting in enhanced self-efficacy and motivation (Cacioppo et al., 2015; Nindle et al., 2018; Nindle et al., 2013).

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework used for this study examined both Resilience Theory and Adult Learning Theory. In particular, this study's

framework was built to examine Resilience Theory through the lens of Adult Learning Theory with a specific focus on a population of soldiers that endured increased perceptions of stress as adult learners. This study set a goal to approach a formal tie between the theories of Adult Learning to the current process-based resilience construct. The understanding that Adult Learners leverage previous experience and that one's ability to rebound from adversity were heavily leaned upon for this study. The conduction of this study through the combined lens of resilience theory and adult learning theory were important, as it set an important distinction of soldiers as adult learners that could learn the skills to overcome their current adversities.

Implementing the Resilience Theory Framework into the Study

While the theoretical construct of resilience is a contested concept, this study chose to address resilience as a process rather than an end-state fixed in each soldier. This process-based approach to resilience is in line with the views of multiple research groups including Dray et al. (2017), Lines et al. (2019), Van Breda (2018), and Wang et al. (2017). However, this study intended to take their works and expand upon the knowledge by applying the process-based approach and a focus on thriving through behavioral change inherent in resilience theory to a group of National Guard soldiers. The process-based view of resilience suggested that by enhancing one's resilience their self-efficacy is also elevated which supported the overall goal of this study (Black et al., 2017; Cacioppo et al., 2015; Cassidy, 2015; Lester et al., 2011c; Nindle et al., 2018; Nindle et al., 2013).

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Development of self-efficacy as a by-product of resilience theory was vital to this study and was built upon the foundational work of Bandura (1982) where he described a concept of self-agency inherent in self-efficacy. Bandura (1982) expanded on this empowerment of self to thrive in that enhanced internal agency promoted positive outcomes in behavioral change and task starting behaviors. Understanding that self-efficacy is a by-product of enhancing the process of resilience across a spectrum of stressors experienced supported the needs of the soldiers effectively tying together resilience and performance (Bandura, 1982; Black et al., 2017; Cassidy, 2015; Nindle et al., 2018; Nindle et al., 2013). This is an important theoretical view of the construct as the process approach suggested that the process can be learned and that anyone can improve or digress their resilience or self-efficacy.

A movement in resilience theory that further added credence to this study was described by Bolton et al. (2017), in that the process-based approach to resilience and, its ability to be developed to drive positive adaptation in people under stress, can be applied to practitioners using solution-focused treatments. To expand on this concept, there was a movement away from the traditional medical-model where diagnostics were the primary focal point of care, to a model of personal strengths and competency-based treatments that worked to empower the patient by leveraging their internal strengths and their external resources to thrive (Bolton et al., 2017). This movement was of value to this study in that the target population was traditional National Guardsmen that were only in uniform one-weekend a month and two-weeks a year, they did not have the continuous

oversight for which their Active Duty counterparts had access. This conceptual movement in resilience theory lends itself well to the National Guard soldier population.

Examining Resilience Theory through the Lens of Adult Learning Theory

Examining the construct of resilience as a process from the perspective of Adult Learning Theory was the intent of this study. The Adult Learning Theory's implementation into the military population has been a point of contention in the Army's professional military education (PME) curriculum and courses. The Army's PME courses were designed as basic-level military education courses to transition a civilian to a soldier, develop soldiers and officers, or to have established a special skillset (Pierson, 2017). However, Pierson (2017) noted that a sizable portion of the Army's PME were designed as advanced-level education that would benefit from implementation of Adult Learning Theory. Accounting for the variance in level and purpose of military education courses, it became a point of note that military education was able to be adapted to enhance educational outcomes through implementation of Adult Learning Theory's concepts (Pierson, 2017; Wendt, 2018)

Adult Learning Theory's implementation into PME and other aspects of the Army's education systems was important due to soldiers qualifying as non-traditional or adult learners. Adult learners were defined within the Adult Learning Theory as those non-traditional learners that were 25 years of age or older (Malik, 2016; McCall et al., 2018; Pierson, 2017; Yarbrough, 2018). Soldiers can join the military with parental consent at the age of 17-years old and can serve up until they are 61-years of age, which presented with some overlap with the

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minimum age of an adult learner according to the Adult Learning Theory (Malik, 2016; McCall et al., 2018; Pierson, 2017). Soldiers were generally considered non-traditional learners not-solely based on their age but also on the nature of education formats implemented across both the basic- and advanced-level courses (Pierson, 2017).

Adult Learning Theory applies four principles and makes a series of assumptions regarding the adult learner population. The four principles applied through Adult Learning Theory are the need to involve adult learners in the learning process development and evaluation, the roles positive and negative experiences play in activities of learning, the need to establish relevance to the adult learner to increase learning motivation, and the problem-centered versus content-oriented approach to learning (Mukhalalati & Taylor, 2019; McCall et al., 2018). These assumptions include that adult learner are self-directed learners, in need of understanding as to why the learning must occur, known to draw heavily from their previous experiences, more drawn to problem-based learning, ready to learn as a coping mechanism to real-life scenarios, and are intrinsically motivated in their learning process (Malik, 2016; Pierson, 2017; Teaching Excellence in Adult Literacy, 2011). An educator that has developed a thorough understanding and comprehension of the learning process of adult learners supports success in conceptual translation between the learner and instructor (Kenner & Weinerman, 2011; Malik, 2016; McCall et al., 2018).

The Army's Training and Doctrine Command (TRADOC) changed its verbiage focus from terms such as 'training' to more Adult Learning Theory appropriate terms like

'education' as it more accurately reflected the intent of the Army's PME (Pierson, 2017). Adult Learning Theory has seen a research increase over the last decade as the population of adult learners has seen notable increases in academia (McCall et al., 2018). Considering both research groups' findings between McCall et al. (2018) work on general education and adult learners and Pierson's (2017) work on soldiers as adult learners, it was suggested that with the increased focus on implementing Adult Learning Theory for the appropriate audiences and non-traditional educational nature of soldiers it was worth expanding the Army's educational training to be one of more Adult Learning Theory focus.

This study leveraged resilience theory's process-approach to build upon the informal and formal entrance to the learning process of adult learners. It was important to account for how adult learners' varied experiences acted to either hinder or reinforce their motivation to succeed (Bandura, 1982; Kenner & Weinerman, 2011; McCall et al., 2018; Malik, 2016). Adult Learning Theory was important to this study's framework in that defining the soldier as an adult learner and both leveraging their internal motivations and developing their individual learning needs helped to facilitate success in lifestyle changes that support long term resilience and growth.

Adult Learning Theory in the MRT Curriculum

The Army's MRT curriculum was built around the needs of the adult learners. Reivich's (2014) Master Resilience Training Trainer Manual incorporated multiple Adult Learning Theory concepts to enable optimal translation of concepts to the adult learners. These concepts include self-reflection, problem-based learning, and self-directed learning (McCall et al., 2018;

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TEAL, 2011; Yarbrough, 2018). Colvin and Taylor (2012) described the ages of the typical unit MRT, the soldier training the skillsets, in the ranges of 26-35 years of age which qualified the trainers as adult learners. This knowledge of the age of the trainer means that the coursework should be designed to support adult learning. Thus, the previously mentioned methods are valid not just in the formal training but also in the implementation to the force to enable success in learning for all soldiers (Pierson, 2017).

Adult Learning Theory suggested that there is value in self-reflection for adult learners (McCall et al., 2018; Mukhalalati & Taylor, 2019; TEAL, 2011; Yarbrough, 2018). Three of the MRT skills (Hunt the Good Stuff, ATC Model, and Detect Icebergs) were built around the concept or skill of self-reflection and its ability to enhance either optimism or self-awareness (McCall et al., 2018; Mukhalalati & Taylor, 2019; Reivich, 2014; TEAL, 2011; Yarbrough, 2018). Yarbrough (2018) suggested that self-reflection was nested within Vygotsky's 'Zone of Proximal Development', a component of Social Development Theory. In the Zone of Proximal Development, the learners worked to identify gaps of ability and developed their skills around the identified gap (Yarbrough, 2018). The skill of self-reflection acted to enable self-awareness and sets the stage for problem-based learning's implementation in education.

Problem-based learning has also been cited as an effective approach to Adult Learning Theory's implementation (Malik, 2016; Mukhalalati & Taylor, 2019; TEAL, 2011; Yarbrough, 2018). Yarbrough (2018) described how problem-based learning falls within both transformational learning and critical reflection which were supported theories to the Adult

Learning Theory. The problem-based learning approach was seen nested in almost every MRT skillset's participant guide, which allowed the learners to see how to implement resilience into their daily lives (Reivich, 2014). Problem-based learning assisted in demonstrating to the adult learner their motivation for self-determined learning.

Self-directed learning has been described as a necessity for adult learners (Malik, 2016; Mukhalalati & Taylor, 2019; Pierson, 2017; TEAL, 2011; Yarbrough, 2018). Mukhalalati and Taylor (2019) described adult learners as intrinsically motivated learners. This concept of intrinsic motivation supports Pierson's (2017) description of self-directed learners as learners that require little to no guidance or direction in their studies. The CSF2 program required soldiers to take the GAT annually, the GAT identifies soldier strengths and weaknesses in each of the supported areas of fitness that comprise the Army's view of resilience (HQDA, 2014; HQDA, 2017a; Peterson et al., 2011). Lester et al. (2013) described a series of 27 self-directed courses that the CSF2 program provided to soldiers to enhance their resilience. Each soldier's GAT results were used to provide them with a series of self-directed courses that they could progress through to improve areas of weakness (Lester et al., 2013).

Application of the Framework to the Study

The MRT curriculum was designed to teach soldiers the skills to become more resilient when dealing with stress and strife by using Adult Learning Theory (Casey, 2011; McCall et al., 2018; Reivich, 2020; Reivich et al., 2011). The MRT curriculum was further developed to enhance the competencies of self-awareness,

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self-regulation, mental agility, optimism, strengths of character, and connection (Casey, 2011; Reivich, 2020; Reivich et al., 2011). McCall et al. (2018) described a constructivist approach to Adult Learning Theory where learners were exposed to strategies supporting self-inquiry, discovery, and problem-based learning to drive awareness of skills for critical thinking and overall awareness of overarching themes. This conceptually applied to all six of the MRT curriculum's competencies (Casey, 2011; McCall et al., 2018; Reivich, 2020; Reivich et al., 2011).

The theory that the construct of resilience is a process that promotes self-efficacy when combined with the Adult Learning Theory's assumptions of adult learners provided this study a framework for success based on the research questions and hypotheses (Black et al., 2017; Cacioppo et al., 2015; Dray et al., 2017; Kenner & Weinerman, 2011; Lines et al., 2019; McCall et al., 2018; Malik, 2016). Through examining Adult Learning Theory and how the theory could effectively support the translation of the resilience process to the soldiers it was possible to establish optimal outcomes not only in perception of resilience in the face of strife but also in healthy lifestyle choices that supported meeting the Army's fitness and body composition requirements (Black et al., 2017; Cacioppo et al., 2015; Dray et al., 2017; Kenner & Weinerman, 2011; Lines et al., 2019; Malik, 2016; McCall et al., 2018). These supporting theories appeared to build a bridge of educational success in support of soldier improvement.

Methodology

This study implemented a quantitative methodology to collect data on soldier perception of resilience and their application of

resilience strategies. This study was a quasi-experimental, ex post facto design for outcome comparison.

Study Population and Sample

This study examined the effectiveness of the Wellness Camp intervention as a resilience-based intervention in improving soldier perception and application of resilience. The state hosting this study had a total force of approximately 9000 Soldiers (Army Public Health Center [APHC], 2020; Headquarters, Department of the Florida Army National Guard [HQFLARNG], 2020). Approximately 1080 soldiers were eligible for the wellness camp intervention. The intervention has had approximately 500 soldiers that have attended the Wellness Camp resilience-based intervention over 10 iterations conducted from 2015 to 2019 (HQFLARNG, 2020). This established a study population of 500 Army National Guard soldiers.

The sample examined in this study were the soldiers that attended the fiscal year 2019 Wellness Camp classes. These two classes 009 and 010, were conducted in January and June of 2019. Class 009 had n=42 soldiers that completed the intervention and class 010 had n=45 soldiers that completed the intervention. This establishes a study sample of n=87 soldiers.

Instrumentation

The National Guard hosting state's Wellness Camp had implemented two separate surveys in the measurement of both perception and application of resilience. This study used the ex post facto data gathered by the R2 Program from these surveys for quantitative measurement of soldier outcomes. These surveys were the Ohio State University's Brief Resilience Scale (BRS) and the Test of Performance Strategies (TOPS) survey. The surveys were

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selected for their validity, reliability, and consistency in their ability to measure perception of resilience as a single construct (BRS) and their ability to measure the perception of use of specific resilience strategies in fitness efforts (Hidalgo-Rasmussen & Gonzalez-Betanzos, 2019; Lourido et al., 2018; Neves et al., 2018; Okan, 2017; Smith et al., 2008; Thomas et al., 1999; Windle et al., 2011).

Data Collection

The data collected for this study came from pre-existing data sources. The primary data collected for this study was the pre-intervention and post-intervention BRS and TOPS survey results. Pre-intervention data that this study used was gathered on day one of the intervention. Post-intervention data this study used was collected on day 14 of the intervention. The BRS and TOPS data was provided from the National Guard's Ready & Resilient Program's (R2P) historical records.

Analysis of Data

Data Preparation

The ex post facto data was collected by the Army National Guard and provided in a de-identified manner to the researcher. Each of the 87 soldiers that participated in one of the 2019 resilience-based Wellness Camp interventions were categorized by gender (according to each soldiers' DEERS profile) and age bracket (based on the Army's Body Composition Program or ABCP age brackets). Both their pre- and post-intervention Brief Resilience Scale (BRS) and Test of Performance Strategies (TOPS) responses were provided to the researcher in a de-identified manner.

The researcher aligned each participants' total outcomes for both the pre- and post- BRS assessment of perception of resilience to the

appropriate de-identified profile. The researcher aligned the averages of portions of the TOPS' questions according to their alignment with each research question. Goal Setting (GS) data was established by averaging the pre- and post-responses from questions 1, 2, 12, 13, and 19. Emotion Control (EC) data was established by averaging the pre- and post- responses from questions 3, 4, 6, 11, 14, and 18. Imagery (IM) data was established by averaging the pre- and post- responses from questions 7, 9, 10, and 15. Energy Activation (EA) data was established by averaging the pre- and post- responses from questions 5, 8, 16, 17.

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 presents a descriptive analysis of categorical study participant characteristics. Data indicated that the sample was about three-quarter male ($n=63$; 72.4%) and one-quarter female ($n=24$; 27.6%). The sample was predominantly in the age bracket of 21-27 years old ($n=45$; 51.7%), with representation in the other age brackets as follows: 17-20 ($n=16$; 18.4%), 21-27 ($n=20$; 23.0%), and 40+ ($n=6$; 6.9%).

Table 1

Descriptive Analysis of Categorical Demographic Characteristics (n=87)

Variable	%	N
Gender		
Male	72.4	63
Female	27.6	24
Age Bracket		
17-20	18.4	16

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21-27		45
	51.7	
28-39		20
	23.0	

Table 2 presented a descriptive analysis of this study variables, including study pretest and posttest scores by performance area. The distribution of all the scores were approximately normal as the skewness and kurtosis were not approximately two times each respective standard error of each.

Table 2

Descriptive Analysis of Pretest and Posttest Scores (n=87)

Variable	M (SD)	Skew (SE)	Kurtosis (SE)
Brief Resilience Scale (BRS)			
Pretest Scores	22.14 (4.47)		
6.00-30.00	-0.48 (0.26)	1.21 (0.51)	
Posttest Scores	23.90 (3.40)		
12.00-30.00	-0.21 (0.26)	0.55 (0.51)	
Pre/Post Difference Scores	1.76 (4.95)		-
9.00-12.00	-0.21 (0.26)	-0.52 (0.51)	
Goal Setting (GS)			
Pretest Scores	3.15 (0.75)		
1.60-5.00	0.35 (0.26)	0.09 (0.51)	
Posttest Scores	3.87 (0.67)		
2.20-5.00	-0.36 (.26)	0.08 (0.51)	
Pre/Post Difference Scores	0.72 (0.91)		-
2.60-3.00	-0.13 (.26)	1.60 (0.51)	
Emotion Control (EC)			
Pretest Scores	3.09 (0.46)		
1.43-4.00	-0.82 (0.26)	1.57 (0.51)	
Posttest Scores	3.40 (0.45)		
2.29-5.00	0.87 (0.26)	2.53 (0.51)	

Pre/Post Difference Scores 0.28 (0.51) -
0.72-1.70 0.43 (0.26) 0.12 (0.51)

Imagery (IM)

Pretest Scores 2.65 (0.53)
1.25-3.80 -0.34 (0.26) 0.12 (0.51)

Posttest Scores 3.30 (0.46)

2.25-4.75 0.21 (0.26) 0.64 (0.51)

Pre/Post Difference Scores 0.65 (0.68)

-0.81-3.00 0.87 (0.26) 1.65 (0.51)

Energy Activation (EA)

Pretest Scores 3.06 (0.58)

1.50-4.25 -0.29 (0.26) -0.15 (0.51)

Posttest Scores 3.59 (0.51)

2.50-5.00 0.37 (0.26) 0.09 (0.51)

Pre/Post Difference Scores 0.53 (0.68)

-1.00-2.00 0.22 (0.26) 0.03 (0.51)

Note: SD= Standard Deviation.

Table 3 presents an independent-samples t-test analysis of pre/post change scores by demographic characteristics. Data indicated that pre/post change scores were not significantly related to gender nor age bracket, as follows: BRS gender, $t(85)=-1.50, p=.14$, age bracket, $F(3,86)=-0.44, p=.72$; GS gender, $t(81)=-0.41, p=.68$, age bracket, $F(3,83)=0.31, p=.82$; EC gender, $t(85)=0.63, p=.53$, age bracket, $F(3,86)=1.58, p=.20$; IM gender, $t(85)=0.10, p=.55$, age bracket, $F(3,86)=0.25, p=.86$; EA gender, $t(85)=0.83, p=.41$, age bracket, $F(3,86)=1.27, p=.29$. These data demonstrated that neither gender nor age had a statistically significant relationship to this study's findings.

Table 3

Independent Samples T-Test and one-way ANOVA Analysis of Pre/Post Change Scores by Demographic Characteristics (n=87)

Variable (SD)	t/F(df)	n	p	M
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BRS				Male	63	0.30
Gender				(0.52)		
	-1.50 (85)	0.14		Female	24	0.23
Male				(0.48)		
(4.92)				Age Bracket		
Female					1.58 (3,86)	0.20
(4.89)				17-20	16	0.26
Age Bracket				(0.40)		
	-0.44 (3,86)			21-27	45	0.20
0.72				(0.43)		
17-20				28-39	20	0.49
(5.45)				(0.62)		
21-27				40+	6	0.32
(5.05)				(0.80)		
28-39				IM		
(5.01)				Gender		
40+					0.10 (85)	0.55
(4.95)				Male	63	0.62
GS				(0.68)		
Gender				Female	24	0.72
	-0.41 (81)	0.68		(0.66)		
Male				Age Bracket		
(0.74)					0.25 (3,86)	0.86
Female				17-20	16	0.69
(0.80)				(0.85)		
Age Bracket				21-27	45	0.61
	0.31 (3,83)	0.82		(0.62)		
17-20				28-39	20	0.74
(0.73)				(0.73)		
21-27				40+	6	0.53
(0.82)				(0.45)		
28-39				EA		
(0.67)				Gender		
40+					0.83 (85)	0.41
(0.75)				Male	63	0.57
EC				(0.65)		
Gender				Female	24	0.43
	0.63 (85)	0.53		(0.76)		

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Age Bracket

	1.27 (3,86)	0.29
17-20 (0.68)	16	0.28
21-27 (0.70)	45	0.52
28-39 (0.68)	20	0.70
40+ (0.46)	6	0.71

Results

Table 4 presents a repeated measures general linear model examining pre- to post-intervention changes in mean scores. Multivariate analysis indicated, that while including study participant age as a covariate, changes in pretest to post scores remained statistically significant for the following: BRS $F(1, 86)=10.99, p<.0001$; GS $F(1, 86)=54.53, p<.0001$; EC $F(1, 86)=27.15, p<.0001$; IM $F(1, 86)=80.25, p<.0001$; and EA $F(1, 86)=52.77, p<.0001$. Furthermore, the analysis evidenced the following Partial Eta Squared effect sizes according to the G*Power analysis completed earlier: BRS medium effect size of .11; GS large effect size of .39; EC medium effect size of .24; IM large effect size of .48; and EA large effect size of .38.

Table 4

Repeated Measures General Model Examining Pretest to Posttest Score Changes While Controlling for the Effect of Study Participant Age (n=87)

Timepoint	n	M (SD)
F(df)	p	PES ¹
BRS		
10.99 (1, 86)	0.001	0.11¹

Pretest	87	22.14
(4.47)		
Posttest	87	23.90 (0.00)

GS

54.53 (1, 86)	0.001	0.39²
Pretest	87	3.15
(0.75)		
Posttest	87	3.88 (0.67)

EC

27.15 (1, 86)	0.001	0.24¹
Pretest	87	3.10
(0.46)		
Posttest	87	3.38 (0.45)

IM

80.25 (1, 86)	0.001	0.48²
Pretest	87	2.65
(0.53)		
Posttest	87	3.30 (0.46)

EA

52.77 (1, 86)	0.001	0.38²
Pretest	87	3.06
(0.58)		
Posttest	87	3.59 (0.51)

¹Partial Eta Squared Effect Size of 0.09 is a medium effect

²Partial Eta Squared Effect Side of 0.25 is a large effect

Initial examination and comparison of the pre- and post-intervention data was conducted using a Multivariate analysis. This demonstrated that each mean value finding per performance area had a statistically significant change ($p<0.001$) and directionality of the findings were in the preferred direction.

Research Question 1

This study's first research question examined the potential statistically significant relationship attendance of the two-week resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention had with soldier perception of their resilience as measured on the BRS when compared between pre- and post-intervention evaluation.

Data analysis indicated a statistically significant relationship was found between the pre- and post-intervention difference measure of 1.76 ($SD=4.95$), $F(1,86)=10.99$, $p<0.001$, and evidenced a medium effect size ($PES=0.113$) for perception of resilience between the pre- and post-intervention data sets. A one-way ANOVA was conducted to look for differences between age brackets on the findings and no statistically significant differences were found between age brackets on reported outcomes ($F(3,86)=0.44$, $p=0.72$). Additionally, an Independent Samples T-Test was conducted on the data set to look for differences based on gender on the outcomes; the Levene's Test for Equality of Variance did not find any statistically significant differences ($F=0.01$, $p=0.92$) with the overall T-Test ($t(85)=-1.50$, $p=0.14$). A Shapiro-Wilk's test for normality was not statistically significant for normality on outcomes ($p=0.30$).

Research Question 2

This study's second research question examined the potential statistical significance relationship attendance of the two-week resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention had with soldier application of the Goal Setting (GS) resilience strategy when compared between pre- and post-intervention evaluation.

Data analysis indicated a statistically significant relationship was found between the pre- and post-intervention difference measure of

0.72 ($SD=0.91$), $F(1,86)=54.54$, $p<0.001$, and evidenced a large effect size ($PES=0.388$) for GS application outcomes between the pre- and post-intervention data sets. A one-way ANOVA was conducted to look for differences between age brackets on the findings and no statistically significant differences were found between age brackets on reported outcomes ($F(3,86)=0.31$, $p=0.82$). Additionally, an Independent Samples T-Test was conducted on the data set to look for differences based on gender on the outcomes; the Levene's Test for Equality of Variance did not find any statistically significant differences ($F=0.29$, $p=0.60$) with the overall T-Test ($t(81)=-0.41$, $p=0.68$). A Shapiro-Wilk's test for normality was statistically significant for normality on outcomes ($p=0.03$); when controlling for outliers ($n=83$) a Paired-Sample T-Test resulted in a difference score of 0.68 ($SD=0.75$), $t(82)=-8.32$, $p<0.001$ showing despite the normality outliers the data set's outcomes still resulted in a statistically significant relationship to the intervention.

Research Question 3

This study's third research question examined the potential statistical significance relationship attendance of the two-week resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention had with soldier application of the Emotion Control (EC) resilience strategy when compared between pre- and post-intervention evaluation.

Data analysis indicated a statistically significant relationship was found between the pre- and post-intervention difference measure of 0.28 ($SD=0.51$), $F(1,86)=27.15$, $p<0.001$, and evidenced a medium effect size ($PES=0.240$) for EC application outcomes between the pre- and post-intervention data sets. A one-way ANOVA was conducted to look for differences between

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age brackets on the findings and no statistically significant differences were found between age brackets on reported outcomes ($F(3,86)=1.58$, $p=0.20$). Additionally, an Independent Samples T-Test was conducted on the data set to look for differences based on gender on the outcomes; the Levene's Test for Equality of Variance did not find any statistically significant differences ($F=0.02$, $p=0.89$) with the overall T-Test ($t(85)=0.63$, $p=0.53$). A Shapiro-Wilk's test for normality was not statistically significant for normality on outcomes ($p=0.20$).

Research Question 4

This study's fourth research question examined the potential statistical significance relationship attendance of the two-week resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention had with soldier application of the Imagery (IM) resilience strategy when compared between pre- and post-intervention evaluation.

Data analysis indicated a statistically significant relationship was found between the pre- and post-intervention difference measure of 0.65 ($SD=0.68$), $F(1,86)=80.25$, $p<0.001$, and evidenced a large effect size ($PES=0.483$) for IM application outcomes between the pre- and post-intervention data sets. A one-way ANOVA was conducted to look for differences between age brackets on the findings and no statistically significant differences were found between age brackets on reported outcomes ($F(3,86)=0.25$, $p=0.86$). Additionally, an Independent Samples T-Test was conducted on the data set to look for differences based on gender on the outcomes; the Levene's Test for Equality of Variance did not find any statistically significant differences ($F=0.10$, $p=0.75$) with the overall T-Test ($t(85)=0.10$, $p=0.55$). A Shapiro-Wilk's test for normality was statistically significant for

normality on outcomes ($p<0.001$); however, when controlling for the outliers ($n=83$) the Paired-Sample T-Test resulted in a mean value of -0.56 ($SD=0.54$), $t(82)=-9.42$, $p<0.001$ showing despite the normality outliers the data set's outcomes still resulted in a statistically significant relationship to the intervention.

Research Question 5

This study's final research question examined the potential statistical significance relationship attendance of the two-week resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention had with soldier application of the Energy Activation (EA) resilience strategy when compared between pre- and post-intervention evaluation.

Data analysis indicated a statistically significant relationship was found between the pre- and post-intervention difference measure of 0.53 ($SD=0.68$), $F(1,86)=52.77$, $p<0.001$, and evidenced a large effect size ($PES=0.380$) for EA application outcomes between the pre- and post-intervention data sets. A one-way ANOVA was conducted to look for differences between age brackets on the findings and no statistically significant differences were found between age brackets on reported outcomes ($F(3,86)=1.27$, $p=0.29$). Additionally, an Independent Samples T-Test was conducted on the data set to look for differences based on gender on the outcomes; the Levene's Test for Equality of Variance did not find any statistically significant differences ($F=0.60$, $p=0.44$) with the overall T-Test ($t(85)=0.83$, $p=0.41$). A Shapiro-Wilk's test for normality was not statistically significant for normality on outcomes ($p=0.052$).

The overall results showed that a statistically significant relationship was found for all areas of this study and that these results

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were not shown to be statistically different between age brackets or gender groups. The current study builds upon the research conducted on Active Duty Army soldiers that discovered an association between resilience levels and aspects of behavior that can either harm or benefit a person's military career (Curley et al., 2020; Curley & Warner, 2017; Harms et al., 2013; Lester et al., 2011b). Further, this study approached the research from the perspective addressing self-efficacy as a by-product of resiliency training (Black et al., 2017; Cacioppo et al., 2015; Cassidy, 2015; Lester et al., 2011c; Nindle et al., 2018; Nindle et al., 2013). The findings lend themselves to expand the current body of literature on the influence of resilience on service members.

Conclusion

The overarching findings for this study were statistically significant relationships between the intervention and post-intervention mean value outcomes for perception of resilience, application of GS, application of EC, application for IM, and application of EA. The intervention resulted in large effect sizes being found for application of GS, application of IM, application of EA. Medium effect sizes were found for perception or resilience and EC. The sample increased their perception of resilience, and applications of all four strategies (GS, EC, IM, and EA). The instructional methodology implemented, where the resilience training materials were presented through the lens of the Adult Learning Theory could have played an important role in the noted findings and success of the intervention. The sample age-brackets that were within the Adult Learning Theory's age ranges of 25 years-old and older had enhanced outcomes at post-intervention testing for the

areas of application of GS, application of EC, and application of EA. However, the younger age brackets seemed to demonstrate elevated outcomes in the areas of perception of resilience and application of IM. The Army's implementation of Adult Learning Theory across all aspects of Professional Military Education (PME) and the fact that soldiers are considered non-traditional learners supported the use of Adult Learning Theory in this intervention (Pierson, 2017). These data showed that the sample's participation in the two-week resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention resulted in enhanced resilience and perception of application of various resilience strategies.

The findings of statistically significant relationships between pre- and post-intervention testing for perception of resilience, and perception of application of resilience strategies for performance (GS, EC, IM, and EA) in traditional M-Day (non-full time) National Guard soldiers lend themselves to support a need for enhanced resilience training in the reserve components of the Army and build upon the findings of the foundational research conducted on the Army's MRT program. Army doctrine currently requires a decreased frequency of resiliency training for reserve components (HQDA, 2014; HQDA, 2017a), yet the reserve components are suggested to be the component of the Army that could benefit most from enhanced self-efficacy, a by-product of enhanced perception of resilience (Black et al., 2017; Cacioppo et al., 2015; Cassidy, 2015; Lester et al., 2011c; Nindle et al., 2018; Nindle et al., 2013).

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